

Formulation And Evaluation of Oral Disintegrating Tablet of Doxylamine Succinate

Ankit Lodhi*, Sudha Vengurlekar, Sachin Kumar Jain

University Institute of Pharmacy, Oriental university, Indore M.P

ABSTRACT

Formulation of oral disintegrating tablet containing Doxylamine succinate was done in which at primary stage we studied and work on the literature reviews of various research and review articles regarding oral disintegrating tablet and antiemetic drugs. Then in next step working on formulation so we studied various excipient and their action. After selection of excipients, preformulation study was performed in which drug identity, solubility and drug excipient interaction or compatibility was done. The different ratio of polymer and drug was putted in stability chamber for 30 days at 37°C temperature and 75% RH and observe the change in physical appearance and performed TLC for determination of retention factor. The oral disintegrating tablet was punched using rotatory punching machine and evaluation of tablet was done in which weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, disintegration time, wetting time, in vitro dissolution and stability studies was performed. The medication of antiemetic as by oral disintegrating tablet formulation was provided for the prevention and treatment of nausea and vomiting. The bioavailability of Doxylamine succinate is enhanced was formulating oral disintegrating dosage form and hepatic metabolism was also avoided by choosing these formulation. One biggest problem that is dysphagia (difficulty in swallowing) was also overcome by this medication. The oral disintegrating tablet of Doxylamine succinate not only gives the rapid onset of action but also enhance the permeability through site of administration. So this type of medication is quite helpful for the patient and next generation.

Keywords: Doxylamine succinate, antiemetic, in vitro dissolution, sodium starch glycolate, oral disintegrating tablet, nausea and vomiting.

INTRODUCTION

Tablet: Tablet is a solid dosage forms each containing a unit dose of one or more medicaments with or without suitable excipients. Tablets may be swallowed whole or being chewed. Some are dissolved or dispersed in water before administration. Some are put in oral cavity, where the active ingredient is liberated at a predetermined rate. Implants or passeries may also be presented in form of tablet. Tablet may vary in shape and differ greatly in size and weight depending on the amount of medicinal substance and the intended mode of administration. Tablets are usually solid, right circular cylinders, the end surfaces of which are flat or convex and the edges of which may be beveled. They may exist in other shapes like triangular, rectangular, etc. They may have lines or break- marks and may bear a symbol or other markings. They are sufficiently

hard to withstand handling without crumbling or breaking.

Advantages of the Tablet dosages form

- Tablets are convenient to use and are an elegant dosage form.
- Objectionable odour and bitter taste can be masked by coating technique. .
- Tablets are generally inexpensive dosage form.
- Suitable for large scale production
- Greatest chemical and microbial stability over all oral dosage form.

2. Material and Method:

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Table No. 1 List of Material

S. No.	Material used	Manufacturer name
01	DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE	MSN laboratories pvt. Ltd.
2	Mannitol	Lobachem Pvt. Ltd.
3	Microcrystalline cellulose	Lobachem Pvt. Ltd.
4	Sodium starch glycolate	Yarrowchem Pvt. Ltd.
5	Povidone	Maple biotech Pvt. Ltd.
6	Saccharin sodium	Lobachem Pvt. Ltd.
7	Magnesium stearate	Lobachem Pvt. Ltd.
8	Sodium hydroxide	Merck
9	Talc	Lobachem Pvt. Ltd.
10	Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate	Merck

PRE FORMULATION STUDIES

UV Spectroscopic study

Preparation of standard stock solution in distilled water

The standard solution containing the drug was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask to which distilled water was added up to mark to produce 1000 μ g/ml⁵³.

Preparation of stock solution in phosphate buffer (pH6.8)

The standard solution containing the drug was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask to which phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was added up to the mark to produce 1000 μ g/ml⁵³.

Determination of λ max in distilled water and phosphate buffer (pH6.8)

By appropriate dilution of standard drug solution with distilled water and phosphate buffer, a solution containing 10 μ g/ml and 5 μ g/ml of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE was scanned within the range of 400 – 200 nm against distilled water and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 for the determination of maximum absorption for the drug in both the solvent.

Preparation of calibration curve

From the above stock solution, 1ml (1000 μ g/ml) of solution was transferred into 10 ml of volumetric flask to prepare 100 μ g/ml working standard, from which aliquots of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 ml were transferred and volume was made up with distilled water into 10 ml volumetric flask to obtain the final concentration range of 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 μ g / ml. The solution was separately analyzed. Same procedure was followed for phosphate buffer pH 6.8⁵⁴.

Drug characterization

Determination of melting point

The capillary tube was taken and its one end was sealed by heating it. The sealed capillary tube was filled with DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE up to 1cm high. The tube was placed in melting point apparatus with a thermometer. The change in the sample was noted on a gradual increase in the temperature. The temperature at which the drug started melting and gets completely melted was noted⁵⁵.

Solubility determination

The shake – flask method is used to determine the solubility of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE in distilled water and phosphate buffer (pH6.8). The sample is which is in a Stopper flask or vial. The vials were sealed and stirred for 10 minutes. Then they were kept on an orbital flask shaker at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 24 hours. After solubilization of the drug, an extra amount of the drug was added to the vial. This process is repeated until saturation solubility of drugs

indicated by the presence of an undissolved drug. Then the mixture is kept aside for 24 hours and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant was separated and diluted with the respective solvent. The concentration of the drug was analyzed at 260 nm and 264 nm using a UV- visible spectrophotometer⁵⁵.

Drug – Excipients compatibility study: Preparation of TLC plate: Firstly silica gel-G slurry prepared by mixing silica gel- G with distilled water in mortar pestle and triturated continuously to make uniform slurry. The slurry was poured uniformly on glass slide and allowed to dry plate in hot air oven at 120 °C. Preparation of sample: The blend of drug with excipients in the ratio of 1:1 was dissolved in water. A capillary tube was used to spot the sample on TLC plates. The diameter of each spot was limited to 0.3 cm. The compounds were spotted at 1 cm above from the bottom of the plate. Development of the solvent system: The solvent system was prepared using ethanol: water (1:1) was used as mobile phase. The 100ml of small beaker was used and the solvent system was poured in it. The glass beaker was lined

with filter paper for prostration with the solvent system for 15-30 minutes⁵⁶.

Stationary Phase – Precoated silica gel – G Mobile Phase – ethanol: water (1:1)

Development of thin layer plate: The previously spotted plates kept in mobile phase. Plates were developed in an ascending manner. When the solvent reached to the mark the plate was removed and the wet plates were dried.

Detection of spot: The iodine chamber was prepared and TLC plate was placed in a chamber. Therefore the plate was removed from chamber and spots was observed and calculate R_f value.

Table. 2 Selection of excipients

S. No.	Excipients	Purpose
1.	Sodium Starch Glycolate	Super disintegrants
2.	Cross povidone	Super disintegrants
3.	Micro crystalline Cellulose	Diluents
4.	Sodium Saccharine	Artificial Sweetener
5.	Magnesium Stearate	Lubricant
6.	Talc	Binder

FORMULATION OF ORAL DISINTEGRATING TABLET OF DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE

The two factor three level design (32) was used for the formulation and optimization of orodispersible tablet of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE and experimental

trials are performed at all 9 possible formulations. In which the amount of sodium starch glycolate and croppovidone were selected as independent variables at three different level : low (-), medium (0), and high (+1) levels. The drug release and disintegration time used as a dependent variable (response).

Table No 3 formulation of oral disintegrating tablet of Doxilamine succinate

S. no.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1.	DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

2.	Sodium Starch Glycolate	2	2	2	4	4	4	6	6	6
3.	crospovidone	2	4	6	2	4	6	2	4	6
4.	Micro crystalline cellulose	41	39	37	39	37	35	37	37	33
5.	Sodium Saccharine	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
6.	Magnesium Stearate	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
7.	Talc	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
	Total(in mg)	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80

Preparation of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE Oral Disintegrating Tablet by Direct Compression Method

All ingredients were accurately weighed and passed through sieve no. 80 and collected in poly bags individually. Then DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE drug was mixed with sodium starch glycolate, crospovidone, microcrystalline cellulose, and sodium saccharine for specified time interval i.e. for 15 minutes. Then, magnesium stearate and talc was added. The compressed tablets were prepared by compressing the blend by rotary tablet compression machine (Aidmach) using 6mm round shaped dies and punches of B-toiling⁵⁷.

EVALUATIONS PARAMETERS:

Pre-compression parameters

Bulk density:

Bulk density was determined by pouring a 10 gm of powder into a 100 ml measuring cylinder through funnel and measure the volume of powder⁵⁸.

Bulk density = Mass of powder / Poured volume of powder

Tapped Density:

10 gm of powder was weigh and transferred into the measuring cylinder. The measuring cylinder was then kept on a mechanical tapper apparatus and tapping of 100 times was done. The volume was occupied by the powdered bed was noted⁵⁸.

Tapped density = Mass of powder / Tapped volume of powder

Angle of repose:

The powder flow property was determined by using the angle of repose. The height of the funnel was adjusted to 4cm above the working slab. The accurately weighed powdered blends were poured through the funnel until pile of powder touches the pipe of the funnel and the height of the powder and the diameter of the powder was noted and calculated. The powder flow property was determined by using angle of repose⁵⁸.

$$\tan\theta = h/r$$

Where,

θ = angle of repose h = height

r = radius

Carr's index: The Carr's index was an indication of compressibility of a powder and calculated using the formula given below⁵⁹.

Carr's = bulk volume –tapped volume/bulk volume x 100

Hausner's ratio:

It is found that the ratio of tapped density and bulk density. A value greater than 1.5 indicates poor flow, between 1.25 and 1.5 added glidant to improve flow and value less than 1.25 indicated good flow⁵⁹.

Hausner's ratio =Tapped density / bulk density

EVALUATION OF PREPARED TABLET

Weight variation

20 tablets were selected randomly and weighed. The average weight was calculated. Not more than two of the individual weights should deviate from the average weight by more than percentage shown in the table and none deviates by more than twice that percentage. In for more than two tablets deviate from the range, retest 20 tablets were done and not more than 2 tablets should deviate from 40 tablets⁶⁰.

Thickness

Tablet thickness was determined using Vernier caliper. The tablet was placed laterally between the jaws of Vernier caliper. Jaws were adjusted to just touch object to be measured. The reading was noted⁶¹.

Hardness

The tablet was placed on the holder. The “0” on Monsanto tester scale was set. The tablet was pressed. The range of Monsanto hardness tester was “0 to 20” kg. The pressure was applied till the tablet breaks. The reading was noted⁶².

Friability

The tablets were weighed before placing in friability apparatus. 10 tablets were placed in the friability test apparatus. Switch was “ON” the mains. Tablets were taken out after 100 revolutions has completed. Re weighed the tablets after deducting⁶².

Wetting time

The tablet was placed at the center of two layers of absorbent paper fitted into a petri-dish. After the paper was thoroughly wetted with distilled water excess water was completely drained out of the dish. The time required for the water to diffuse from the wetted absorbent paper throughout the entire tablet was then recorded using a stop watch⁶³

Water absorption ratio

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small Petri dish containing 6 ml of water. A tablet was put on the tissue paper and allowed to completely wet. The wetted tablets were reweighed. Water absorption ration, R was determined using following equation⁶⁴.

$$R=100 \times \frac{W_a - W_b}{W_a}$$

Where,

W_a = Weight of tablet after water absorption

W_b = Weight of tablet before water absorption

Disintegration Time

One tablet was introduced into each tube and added a disc to each tube. The assembly was suspended in the beaker containing purified water. The apparatus was operated until the tablet completely disintegrates. The time taken was noted for the complete disintegration of the tablet without any remittants. The assembly was removed from water⁶

3. Result and Discussion

Pre formulation studies

Drug characterization

Melting point: Melting point of Doxylamine Succinate was determined by capillary method. The melting point of Doxylamine Succinate was found to be 103 °C which was similar as reported [66].

Table. 4 Melting Point of Doxylamine Succinate

Drug	Observed	Reference
Doxylamine	1020 C- 1050 C	102-107°C

Determination of wave length using UV spectrophotometric analysis:

The maximum wavelength of Doxylamine Succinate was found to be 260 nm. This was found to be similar as required wavelength [66]. The UV spectrum of Doxylamine Succinate drug is shown in the figure 7.2.

Figure 1: Spectrum of Doxylamine Succinate by UV Spectroscopy

Preparation of calibration curves:

The calibration curves of Doxylamine Succinate in various solvents e.g. Distilled water, phosphate buffer pH 6.8 were prepared and shown below [67]:

Table 5: Absorbance data of Doxylamine Succinate in distilled water for preparation of

S.no.	Concentration	Absorbance (mean ± standard deviation)
1	2	0.187
2	4	0.294
3	6	0.441
4	8	0.637
5	10	0.828

Figure 2: Calibration curve of Doxylamine Succinate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Determination of solubility of Doxylamine Succinate in various medium:

The solubility of Doxylamine Succinate in various mediums was studied and the results of study were shown in below table:

Table- 6: Solubility data of Doxylamine Succinate in different mediums

S.NO.	Solvent	Solubility(mg/ml) Mean±SD
1	Distilled water	0.527 µg/ml
2	Phosphate buffer (pH)6.8	0.328 µg/ml

The above solubility data have satisfactory results [68].

The drug (Doxylamine Succinate) was found to be compatible with various excipients which were selected for formulation of oral disintegrating tablet. The compatibility was assessed by TLC and the retention factors of all ratios found similar [69].

Drug- excipient interaction study:

Table 7: Data of drug-excipient interaction study

S.NO.	Drug/ drug + Excipient Ratio (1:1)	Present Day (Rf)	After 8 Days (Rf)	Inference
1.	Drug (Doxylamine Succinate)	0.75	0.72	Minor Change
2.	Drug + Mannitol	0.78	0.71	Minor Change
3.	Drug + Talc	0.72	0.70	Minor Change
4.	Drug+ Magnesium stearate	0.70	0.68	Minor Change
5.	Drug + cross povidone	0.76	0.72	Minor Change
6.	Drug + Sodium saccharine	0.72	0.70	Minor Change
7.	Drug + Sodium starch glycolate	0.76	0.72	Minor Change
8.	Drug+ Microcrystalline cellulose	0.73	0.72	Minor Change

Formulation and Development

Pre Compression Characterization:

Bulk density, Tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, Angle of repose

The bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose of drug excipient mixture were performed and shown in table 7.7. All the results show that mixture possess a good flow property [70].

Table 8: Pre Compression Characterization:

Characterization	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Bulk density (g/cm³)	0.100	0.100	0.95	0.100	0.095	0.100	0.105	0.100	0.100
Tapped density (g/cm³)	0.117	0.125	0.117	0.111	0.117	0.125	0.117	0.111	0.117
Carr's index	14.25	20.00	18.80	9.90	18.80	20.00	10.25	9.90	14.52
Hausner's ratio	0.17	1.25	1.23	1.11	1.23	1.25	1.11	1.11	1.17
Angle of repose (Degree)	27.92	26.56	28.36	27.92	26.10	28.81	27.02	27.02	29.68

Determination of Physicochemical Properties of Oral Disintegrating Tablet

The various physicochemical properties were evaluated like thickness, hardness, weight variation,

friability, drug content, disintegration time, wetting time and the results of the study were shown in below table:

Table 9 Absorbance data of Doxylamine Succinate in distilled water for preparation of calibration curve at 260 nm

S.no.	Concentration	Absorbance (mean \pm standard deviation)
1	2	0.187
2	4	0.294
3	6	0.441
4	8	0.637
5	10	0.828

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Doxylamine Succinate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8**Determination of solubility of Doxylamine Succinate in various medium:**

The solubility of Doxylamine Succinate in various mediums was studied and the results of study were shown in below table:

Table 10 Hardness, Thickness, Percentage Friability and Average weight of Batch F1-F9

Batch	Hardness (Kg/cm ²) \pm SD	Thickness (mm) \pm SD	Percentage Friability(%) \pm SD	Average Weight(mg) \pm SD
F1	2.833 \pm 0.057	3.9 \pm 0.199	0.853 \pm 0.0057	73.3 \pm 2.081
F2	2.9 \pm 0.00	3.73 \pm 0.057	0.776 \pm 0.0152	72.8 \pm 0.577
F3	2.76 \pm 0.057	3.83 \pm 0.115	0.823 \pm 0.0115	73.6 \pm 1.527
F4	2.86 \pm 0.115	3.76 \pm 0.115	0.846 \pm 0.0057	74.2 \pm 2.081
F5	3.16 \pm 0.057	3.93 \pm 0.115	0.783 \pm 0.0115	73.4 \pm 1.154
F6	2.833 \pm 0.057	3.7 \pm 0.099	0.580 \pm 0.010	72.4 \pm 3.00
F7	3.03 \pm 0.057	3.96 \pm 0.152	0.686 \pm 0.0057	73.5 \pm 0.577
F8	2.86 \pm 0.057	3.93 \pm 0.057	0.826 \pm 0.0251	72.6 \pm 1.527
F9	3.16 \pm 0.057	4.03 \pm 0.057	0.686 \pm 0.0057	74.5 \pm 0.577

Table 11 Disintegration Time, Drug Content Uniformity, Water Absorption Ratio and Wetting Time of Batch F1-F9

Batch	Drug Content Uniformity	Wetting Time (seconds)	Water Absorption ratio	Disintegration Time (Seconds)
F1	93.33±2.516	24.33±4.041	51±2.645	106±6.92
F2	89.66±0.5773	22±3.605	49.33±0.577	56.66±3.214
F3	93.66±3.785	22.33±1.527	44.66±4.163	69.66±1.527
F4	96±3.6055	26±4.582	42±3	65±3
F5	98.33±0.5773	18.66±0.577	40±1	53.66±2.309
F6	95±2.645	22.33±2.516	42.33±2.309	53±3.605
F7	98.33±0.5773	18.66±1.527	35±3.605	54.33±4.041
F8	93.66±4.041	22±2.645	36.66±2.516	53±4.582
F9	98.66±0.577	17.66±0.577	32.66±0.577	48.33±0.577

In-vitro drug release study for Oral Disintegrating tablet:

minutes. Based on below results, formulation F9 was selected as best formulation.

The percentage drug release from formulations F1 to F9 was found to be more than 90 % drug within 30

Table 12 Percentage drug release data of F1 to F9 formulation of Oral Disintegrating tablets

S. No.	Time(in min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.	5	44.21	43.02	59.6	60	76.57	63.94	72.23	61.57	77.76
3.	10	82.5	72.23	69.07	81.71	79.73	71.05	76.57	67.89	84.86
4.	15	85.26	82.89	82.5	83.28	85.26	76.18	78.55	81.71	89.6
5.	20	86.84	88.81	84.86	90.39	88.42	83.68	91.18	90	91.18
6.	25	93.15	90.39	86.44	92.76	90	88.81	94.34	92.76	94.34
7.	30	94.73	93.55	94.34	93.15	97.1	91.97	96.71	93.94	97.5

Figure 4 Percentage drug release data of F1 to F9 formulation of Oral Disintegrating tablets

Stability study for Oral Disintegrating tablet

The stability studies of prepared tablets were performed after 1 month and 2 month and found satisfactory results.

Table 13: Stability study for Oral Disintegrating tablet

S.no.	Parameter	Initial Day	After 1 Month	After 2 Month
1.	Average weight	80 mg	80 mg	80 mg
2.	Hardness	3.18 kg/cm ²	3.16 kg/cm ²	3.10 kg/cm ²
3.	Drug content	99.8 %	98.6%	98.6%
4.	Wetting time	16 second	17 seconds	17 seconds
5.	Water absorption ratio	30.2	32.6	32.6
6.	Disintegration	46 seconds	48 seconds	48 seconds

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY

DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE an antihistaminic drug commonly used in nausea and vomiting, bioavailability of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE short i.e. 24% and shows hepatic first pass metabolism the objective of present research is to formulate DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE fast dissolving tablet for fast action.

The main aim of current research is to formulate a Fast dissolving tablet of antihistaminic drug DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE to overcome the following drawback by formulation of fast dissolving tablet of antihistaminic drug of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE.

- For rapid onset of action
- For patient compliance
- For better absorption

The preformulation study of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE was conducted and λ_{max} was found at 260 nm. Melting point was found at 103 °C. This shows that drug is pure. The standard curve of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE was prepared in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (λ_{max} 260 nm) and r^2 value was obtained 0.999, which shows the linearity of absorbance and follows Beer's Lambert law. The different ratio of polymer and drug was putted in stability chamber for 30 days at 37°C temperature and 75% RH and observe the change in physical appearance and performed TLC for determination of retention factor.

The direct compression method was used to formulate and evaluate oral disintegrating tablet of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE. The two factor three level design (32) was used for the formulation and optimization of orodispersible tablet of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE and experimental trials are performed at all 9 possible formulations. In which the amount of sodium starch glycolate and croscarmellose were selected as independent variables at three different level : low (-), medium (0), and high (+1) levels. The drug release and disintegration time used as a dependent variable (response).

Various formulations of oral disintegrating tablet of DOXYLAMINE SUCCINATE. F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F8 & F9 was prepared. The prepared granules was evaluated for different parameters like Bulk density, Tapped density, Angle of repose, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio. which shows the excellent flow properties of formulation

REFERENCE

1. Ubhe santosh tejaswi, Gedam preeti, A brief Overview on Tablet and its Types, *Journal of Advancement in pharmacology* Volume 1, issue,1.
2. Basubiswajit, Bagadiya Abhishek, Makwana sagar, Vipulvora, Batt Devraj and Dharamsi Abhay, formulation and evaluation of fast dissolving tablet of cinnarzine using superdisintegrant blends and subliming material, *journal of advanced pharmaceutical technology and research*, 2011 oct-Dec; 2(4): 266-273.
3. Masih Ashish, kumar Amar, Singh shivam, Tiwari kumar Ajay. Fast dissolving tablet,

International Journal of current pharmaceutical research vol9 , issue 2, 2017.

4. Priyanka joshi, Manju, Mohd Vaseem Fateh, N.G. Raghavendra Rao;(2019) Review on Mouth Dissolving Tablet, *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Volume No.9 ISSN:2231-5691
5. V.N.Deshmukh;(2012) Mouth Dissolving Drug Delivery System: A Review; *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, vol.4,No.1.,pp412-42.
6. Waheeda Nasreen, Zahid Sadek Chowdhury, Yeakuty Marzan Jhanker;(2013) Mouth dissolving tablet- A unique dosage form curtailed for special purpose: a review; *IOSR Journal of pharmacy and Biological sciences*, p-ISSN:2319-7676 Volume 6.
7. Ujjwal Nautiyal, Satinderjeet Singh, Ramandeep Singh, Gopal, SatinderKakar; (2014) Fast Dissolving Tablets as A Novel Boon: A Review, *Journal of Pharmaceutical Chemical and Biological Sciences* 2(1):05-26
8. Gaurav C. Savpure, Azam Z. Shaikh, Sandip A. Tadavi, and Sunil P. Pawar; Review On Mouth Dissolving Tablet, *World Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Sciences*, Volume 8, Issue 3, 1524-1537.
9. Masih Dljit, Gupta Rajesh, Mouth dissolving tablet- A Review, *UK Journal of pharmaceutical and Bioscience* Vol.1(1),18-24,2013.
10. Garg Ashish, M.M Gupta, Mouth dissolving tablet; A Review, *Journal of drug delivery and Therapeutic*; 2013,3(2), 207-214.
11. Sohi Harmik, Sultana Yasmin and, Khar k. taste masking technologies in oral pharmaceutical; Recent development and approaches
12. Bahraini and Sara, Abbas pour Mohammad reza, Kouchak Maryam, Moghadam Taghavi Peoria's Review on fast dissolving system; from tablet to nanofibers,

HOW TO CITE: Ankit Lodhi*, Sudha Vengurlekar, Sachin Kumar Jain, Formulation and Evaluation of Oral Disintegrating Tablet of Doxylamine Succinate, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (2), 241-251. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18806702>